

SOCIAL-PHILOSOPHICAL AND CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONTINUOUS SPIRITUAL EDUCATION SYSTEM

Mannapov Sultanbek

Fergana State University

Professor of the Faculty of Pedagogy-Psychology and Art Studies

orchid ID: 0009-0001-6714-9091

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13999692>

Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the musical heritage factor in the implementation of continuous spiritual education in New Uzbekistan, the possibilities of using examples of musical heritage to increase the effectiveness of the continuous spiritual education system, the future tasks of the musical heritage factor in the process of continuous spiritual education studied. The socio-philosophical and conceptual aspects of the continuous spiritual education system are also analyzed.

Key words: continuous spiritual education, musical heritage, socio-philosophical factor, education, dynamics, harmonization, social state, systemic-functional analysis, theoretical-methodological basis, development, social value, cultural context.

INTRODUCTION. If we look at the lifestyle, standard of living, and economic development of today's advanced traditional countries, we can see that they have created a state system in accordance with their historical, national traditions, values, worldviews and religious beliefs. we will be In this sense, as we are boldly moving from "National revival to national rise" today, we deeply feel that the development of our country and the prospects of our people depend not only on material and economic factors, but also on spiritual and moral factors.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Wide use of examples of musical heritage in the implementation of continuous spiritual education in society and through this, scientific researches on the development of axiological attitude of young people to the national musical heritage, reform of the pedagogical process on the national musical heritage and its preservation, scientific research on determining the axiological attitude to the national musical heritage practical tasks D. Karomatli, T. Levin, Y. Elsner, E. Abdulin, YE. Bodina, O. Bochkareva, E. Burzina, N. Ivanov, L. Koval, V. Rajnikov, A. Rapatskaya, S. Bulatov, Researched by scientists such as B. Azimov, S. Annamuratova, O. Vasilchenko, Sh. Janaydarov, F. Joraev, D. Kamolova, H. Nurmatov, F. Khalilov, A. Hasanov. Also,

the history, theory, characteristics of Uzbek classical musical heritage, folklore songs, R. Abdullaev, S. Begmatov, T. Vizgo, O. Ibrohimov, F. Karomatov, I. Rajabov, T. Gafurbekov, B. Kadirov, Covered in the works of M. Kadirov, E. Fayzullaev.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Inculcating the life-giving principles of our national values into the lifestyle of our historical heritage, striving to live by the exemplary life and activities of our great predecessors is becoming the vital meaning of the lifestyle of every citizen of our society. "National history should be created with a national spirit. Otherwise, it will not have an educational effect. We need to teach our youth to learn from history, to draw conclusions, to arm them with the science of history and historical thinking." After all, the education received by a person during his life determines his position in society. Education is a historical and social phenomenon. It has been formed over time since the beginning of mankind. Education leads a person to maturity. Our ancestors emphasized in their works that education should start from birth and continue to develop throughout life.

Enlightenment leader Abdulla Avloni has such thoughts: "Education should start from the day of birth, it is necessary to strengthen our body, strengthen our morals, and develop our mind."

Human education takes place in five directions: faith education, spiritual education, worldly education, physical education, and spiritual education.

The main criterion of the education of faith is to know, understand and obey the creator.

Spiritual education is closely related to the education of faith in human education. How good and appropriate these upbringings are is determined from the family. Spiritual education is based on the rightness of the heart. That is why a child needs spiritual education.

Secular education teaches balance, honesty, and purity in world affairs.

Physical education is very important for everyone's physical health. If a person is spiritually educated, he does not get involved in sins and bad deeds.

Each type of education has a great role in a person's entry into society and reaching a certain position in it. They complement each other in the development of a person.

Many people are worried about some changes and problems in our spiritual life in recent years. Although a lot of work has been done and is being done in the field of spirituality, they do not have enough results, and the following questions remain open: Why are these efforts not giving the expected results?

Why are there still a lot of low-spirited, poor and downtrodden people around us? Who are those who go against their people and their country and shed the blood of innocent people and why are they doing this? Especially the sad situations that have been observed in our country recently; All of us are worried about the increasing number of crimes committed by our youth.

It is difficult to answer these questions at first glance. In our opinion, if we look for answers to the above questions based on the dialectic of necessity and chance in philosophy, maybe we will find the right answers to them quickly and easily. It should be noted that in the scientific works, articles and books written so far, spirituality has been studied more deeply from the pedagogical and psychological point of view. However, the philosophical aspects of spirituality are not sufficiently covered in these works. However, the methodological basis of spirituality is philosophy. "First of all, this science (fundamentals of spirituality) also relies on the methodology of sciences. The methodology of sciences (information about success) is philosophy, or rather dialectics. The science "Foundations of Spirituality" also analyzes its topics based on this dialectical method and draws theoretical conclusions. Taking this into account, our goal in addressing this topic is to justify the achievements, problems and necessary and accidental processes in the spiritual and educational upbringing of the future generation based on the needs of the times.

A coincidence does not happen by itself, out of nowhere. There is certainly a reason, that is, a reason for the occurrence of an accident. Based on this opinion, we can draw the following conclusion: coincidences in the spiritual life of society do not happen by themselves. All these coincidences, of course, happen under the influence of some reason or basis. Only by learning the essence of these reasons or foundations will we be able to anticipate the occurrences that will have a negative impact on the spiritual life of society. So, what are the possibilities of coincidences in the spiritual life of society?

From the above points, it can be concluded that the occurrence of coincidences in the field of spirituality, or rather, in the spiritual life of society, depends only and only on the activities of people. Another consideration is that, in our view, the probability of unpleasant accidents is very low in a society that is morally high. After all, most of the people living in such a society have a high level of spirituality. A spiritual person knows exactly what is good and what is bad. A spiritual person is well aware of the rightness or wrongness of his actions. So, a spiritual person is less likely to go astray and have accidents. In this place, the ancient Chinese scholar Confucius said: "Everyone goes astray

depending on his character (intelligence). "You can tell if a person is good or humane by the mistakes he makes," is very appropriate. According to Confucius, we can conclude that everyone can get lost in life according to their spiritual potential, that is, they can be exposed to accidents. It can be said that this opinion of Confucius is of great importance in the study of the phenomenon of chance. According to him, mistakes in human life are caused by human behavior. To put it more simply, every single person is the cause of the accidents that happened and are happening in his life. All of them lead to the following conclusion. A person's behavior, intelligence, understanding or spirituality have a great influence on the occurrence of accidents in his life.

At the new stage of society's development, attention to spirituality is considered to have an important place in the country's future. As a mature person, a spiritual person determines the context of the development of society. In this regard, education is recognized as the main factor as a means of determining the strategic goals of spiritual education. In the 1970s and 1980s, efforts were made by UNESCO to prevent the current problems on a global scale, and it was reflected in the lectures devoted to it and researches devoted to education. In particular, important reports such as "There is no limit to learning" prepared by D. Botkin, M. Elmandira, and M. Malits in 1979 can be cited. In it, it is determined that the place and role of spiritual education is incomparable in solving the global problems of our time, as well as in eliminating the gap that has arisen between man and the civilization he created.

Also, based on the philosophical analysis of the concepts of "spirituality" and "personality", the philosopher F.Y. Abramov and V.I. Kudashov in their "Dialogical event and modern knowledge" states in "lim". Thus, saving humanity from a series of disasters in which people themselves perished is evidence that the general and open communication between various systems involved in the organization and maintenance of human life is considered a process dependent on the spiritual environment. Abu Hamid al-Ghazali in his work "Kimiyo Saadat" wrote, "How many calamities will arise that make the heart busy with the world, causing destruction (in both worlds). For example, greed, avarice, envy, enmity and many others. And after he keeps the body as a friend to the world's blessings, his building will be destroyed. And some devote all their efforts to the world and separate themselves from the wealth of their language (spiritual wealth such as kindness, humility, conscience, purity of faith, courage, and nobility) and become close to animals. This means that methods of forming new technologies in spiritual education are always important for humanity.

CONCLUSION. Academician E. Yusupov defines spirituality as follows: "Spirituality is an integral combination of human morals and manners, knowledge, talent, ability, practical skills, conscience, belief, faith, worldview, ideological views. , is a common system that positively affects the development of society.

In fact, spirituality and enlightenment play a very important role in the development of any country. The social and economic condition of a country with mature spirituality and enlightenment of its people will be correspondingly high.

References:

1. Kuranova I.Kh. The role of preschool education in the implementation of continuous spiritual education. Materials of the republican scientific-practical conference on the topic "Actual issues of organizing creative and innovative activities of educators in preschool educational institutions". Andijan, 2020. - P. 212-215.
2. Abramov Yu.F., Kudashov V.I. The phenomenon is dialogic and contemporary. - Irkutsk, 1998. -S. 196
3. Abu Hamid Ghazali. Chemical bliss. - Tashkent: Adolat, 2005. - B. 89.
4. Avloni A. Turkish culture or morals. - Tashkent: Teacher, 1993.
5. Ahmedova O'.N. Formation of new strategic technologies in spiritual education. Scientific progress. Volume 3 | ISSUE 1 | 2022. – B. 321-327.
6. If the economy is the body of society's life, its soul and spirit is spirituality. / The word of the people. January 20, 2021. #13 (7793).
7. Salimov B.L., Mazbutov D., Joraev A. Equality and inequality in social relations are interdependence of laws and customs. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 2022. – B. 11-17.

